

Solute-Solvent Interactions. Part I. Viscosity of Sodium Acetate in Acidic Aqueous Ethanol

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The viscosity of the solution of sodium acetate in acidic aqueous ethanol (10-90% v/v) has been measured at 30°. The viscosities at 30°, 35° and 40° have also been measured for different concentrations of sodium acetate in 50% ethanol. The energy of activation for the viscous flow for different compositions of the salt is given. The viscosity data have been fitted to Jones-Dole equation. The B-coefficient increases with increasing temperature which indicates that sodium acetate behaves as a structure breaker in acidic aqueous ethanol. From the density measurements it is found that the Root's equation is valid only in the lower concentration of sodium acetate in this medium.

AMONG the various methods to study the solute-solvent interactions, that which involves viscous and density data is easier and simpler. The B-coefficient of Jones-Dole equation¹ is a better measure of the interaction of the added electrolyte in a particular medium. This is in accordance with the views of Gurney², Kaminsky³ and Nightingale⁴. To know the effect of solvent on the polarographic parameters such as diffusion current, half-wave potential and polarographic maxima (the study of which is in progress), the nature of composition, interaction and solvent structure are needed. Hence in the present study viscosities of solutions of sodium acetate (supporting electrolyte) in the solvent composed of water, ethanol, 0.03% gelatin (maximum suppressor) and 0.1 N acetic acid (for buffer action) have been measured. Only the composition of ethanol and water is varied keeping the concentration of gelatin and acetic acid constant throughout.

Experimental

Sodium acetate (Analar grade) was used as such. Acetic acid was purified over chromium trioxide. Doubly distilled water was used for preparing various solutions. Gelatin was used without further purification. The viscosity was measured with an Ostwald's viscometer and the density of the solutions using a specific gravity bottle (10 ml capacity). The viscosity coefficients of water used for calculation were 0.8004, 0.7208 and 0.6536 at 30°, 35° and at 40° respectively.

Results and Discussion

The viscosity of sodium acetate in the solvent composed of 10-90% (v/v) ethanol, water, 0.03% gelatin and 0.1 N acetic acid in the concentration range (0.0060 to 0.4M) were determined. The viscosity of sodium acetate decreases in the lower

concentration and increases with the increase of salt concentration. As the ethanol content of the solvent is increased the viscosity increases first and decreases above 70% of ethanol. With increase in temperature decrease of viscosity is observed. The viscosity data have been analysed by means of Jones-Dole equation (1)

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots (1)$$

where η is the viscosity of the solution. η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent, C is the molar concentration and A and B are constants characteristic of the solute electrolyte. The values of A and B of equation (1) are determined from the intercept and slope of the linear plots of $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ vs \sqrt{C} . The plots in all the cases of acidic aqueous ethanol are shown in Fig. 1.

In the Jones-Dole equation A denotes ion-ion interaction and B denotes solute-solvent interaction. In general, the magnitude of A value for common salts appears to be smaller. The A values obtained are negative upto 60% of ethanol content and above 60%, it is positive upto 90% of ethanol content. The value of A increases as the temperature is increased. However, the interpenetration effect (cation-cation⁵⁻⁸) and (cation-anion^{8,9}) which also brings ions together, may be responsible for the increase. The value of A should decrease with rise in temperature which one should expect in view of more violent thermal agitation at higher temperature and reduction of attractive forces. Since A is a measure of ion-ion interaction which assumes significance in very dilute solutions and data reported here are for higher concentrations it would be unwise to make further comments on these values.

B values for sodium acetate is positive in all compositions of the solvent studied here. It may

Fig. 1

TABLE 2—THE VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS A AND B OF JONES-DOLE EQUATION

Composition of ethanol%	A	B
10	-0.144	0.5882
20	-0.086	0.4000
30	-0.122	0.4820
40	-0.062	0.3438
50	-0.054 _a	0.3231
	-0.041 _b	0.3280
	-0.032 _c	0.3333
60	-0.078	0.4737
70	0.016	0.2880
80	0.026	0.3555
90	0.1081	0.3535

(a) denotes at 30°,
 (b) denotes at 35°,
 (c) denotes at 40°.

be noted from Table 2 that the variation of B value with composition of the solvent is not regular indicating that the electrostatic ion-solvent interaction varies with the behaviour of gelatin with the alcohol and acidic content of the medium. The high charge density on the small cation gives rise to strong electrostatic interaction in solution, i.e., the smaller the ion, the stronger the ion-solvent dipole interaction and hence larger the size of the solvated ion in solution. The irregularity in variations of B value may be due to the degree of hydrolysis of gelatin since it is in acid medium. The positive temperature coefficient of B, dB/dT suggests that the salt behaves as a structure breaker in this case. The effect of addition of ethanol in water has been deduced from the viscosity data of binary mixtures of water and ethanol. Viscosity data for binary mixtures have yielded information regarding the nature of the interactions^{10,11}. For the viscosity of such binary mixtures we have used equation (2) suggested by Grunberg and Nissan¹².

$$\ln \eta_{\text{mix}} = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + X_1 X_2 d \quad \dots (2)$$

where η_{mix} is the viscosity of the mixture, η_1 is of the liquid one, η_2 of the liquid second. X_1 and X_2 are the mole fractions of the component of the mixture. d is proportional to w/RT and w is the interchange energy. The parameter has the same significance as given by Guggenheim¹³ in the treatment of regular solution theory and d has been regarded as a better measure of the strength of interaction between the components in solution. The data for d along with excess viscosity and energy of activation are given in Table 3. (i) If $\eta^E > 0$, $d > 0$ and the magnitude of both is large, then strong specific interaction would be present. (ii) If $\eta^E < 0$ but $d > 0$ then weak specific interaction would be present¹⁴ and (iii) if $\eta^E < 0$ and $d < 0$ and the magnitude of both is larger, then specific interaction would be absent. In the present case $\eta^E > 0$, $d > 0$ and the magnitude of both is large at all compositions and temperature (except at 40° where d is negative for the 0.0731 mole fraction of ethanol) suggesting strong specific interactions.

According to Stokes and Mills¹⁵ the viscosity of electrolytic solution incorporates that of solvent plus the contribution from four other sources. Thus

$$\eta = \eta^O + \eta^+ + \eta^A + \eta^E + \eta^D \quad \dots (3)$$

where η^+ is the positive increase in viscosity caused by long range electrostatic interaction; η^E is the positive increase due to the shape and size of an ion, η^A is the increase due to alignment or orientation of the polar molecules by the ionic field and η^D is the decrease in viscosity arising due to the distortion of the solvent structure by the ions. Substituting equation (3) in (1) and eliminating the

contribution due to the Coulombic interaction from both, we get

$$\eta^E + \eta^A + \eta^D = \eta^0 BC$$

Therefore B-coefficient can be discussed in terms of these viscosity effects at a particular concentration and temperature.

The sodium ion having high charge density strongly orient solvent molecules making a sheath of firmly attached layer. The positive and larger value of B-coefficient may be attributed to the strong association between water and ethanol through multiple hydrogen bonding. Thus the solvated ions would lead to larger values of η^E and η^A . This argument holds good for the ions of intermediate size like Na^+ for which $\eta^E + \eta^A \approx \eta^D$. It may be observed from Table 1 that the tempera-

TABLE 1—VISCOSITY OF SODIUM ACETATE IN ACIDIC AQUEOUS ETHANOL

Molarity	η (cp)	$\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0}$	$\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0 C^{1/2}}$
50% ethanol + water + 0.03% gelatin + 0.1N Acetic acid			
0.0000	1.9196(a) 1.6067(b) 1.3688(c)	—	—
0.0062	1.8976(a) 1.6046(b) 1.3615(c)	-0.0115 -0.0013 -0.0053	-0.0322 -0.0167 -0.0046
0.0125	1.9001(a) 1.6056(b) 1.3640(c)	-0.0028 -0.0007 -0.0035	-0.0247 -0.0064 -0.0313
0.0250	1.9080(a) 1.6097(b) 1.3711(c)	-0.0009 0.0019 0.0029	-0.0063 0.0121 0.0182
0.0500	1.9252(a) 1.6197(b) 1.3789(c)	0.0029 0.0031 0.0074	0.0130 0.0362 0.0331
0.1000	1.9490(a) 1.6376(b) 1.4000(c)	0.0153 0.0192 0.0229	0.0483 0.0607 0.0725
0.2000	1.9877(a) 1.6806(b) 1.4362(c)	0.0355 0.0460 0.0492	0.0795 0.1029 0.1100
0.4000	2.0955(a) 1.7660(b) 1.5059	0.0916 0.0991 0.1001	0.1448 0.1569 0.1583

(a) denotes at 30°, (b) denotes at 35°, (c) denotes at 40°.

ture coefficient of viscosity at 50% ethanol increases with increasing concentration of sodium acetate and decrease with rise in temperature as one should expect in view of the larger value of η at higher concentrations and low temperature. The effect of temperature on the viscosity is given by

$$\eta = A e^{\frac{E\eta}{RT}}$$

where A is a constant, $E\eta$ is the activation energy for the viscous flow and other symbols have usual significance. The plots of $\log \eta$ versus $1/T$ for different concentrations of sodium acetate in 50% ethanol are linear. $E\eta$ values were obtained from the slope

of the plots and are given in Table 4. The energy of activation for ethanol water system has also been given in Table 3. $E\eta$ can be related to the work needed to form vacant sites¹⁶ in the solvent matrix and may be regarded as the measure of the structure of the solvent.

TABLE 3—VISCOSITY DATA OF DIFFERENT AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF ETHANOL

Mole fraction of Ethanol	Excess Viscosity η^E	d	Energy of activation $E\eta \times 10^{-3} \text{JM}^{-1}$
Ethanol	—	—	3.47
0.0731	0.4574(a) 0.3577(b) 0.2861(c)	6.5750 5.8695 -0.0974	4.63
0.1738	0.8874(a) 0.6333(b) 0.5752(c)	3.4779 4.5197 4.2356	4.73
0.3213	0.9742(a) 0.7792(b) 0.6342(c)	3.3834 3.1275 2.8954	6.94
0.5580	0.6836(a) 0.5535(b) 0.4539(c)	2.1651 2.0159 1.8683	7.29

(a) denotes at 30°
(b) " " 35°
(c) " " 40°.

TABLE 4—ENERGY OF ACTIVATION FOR THE VISCOUS FLOW OF SODIUM ACETATE IN 50% ETHANOL

Molarity	$E\eta \times 10^{-3} \text{JM}^{-1}$
0.0000	5.61
0.0062	3.95
0.0125	6.03
0.0250	4.79
0.0500	5.54
0.1000	6.41
0.2000	7.15
0.4000	8.42

Densities of the salt solutions in acidic aqueous ethanol at different compositions of alcohol have been found to fit the Root's equation¹⁷ (4) only in the lower concentrations. As the concentration increases some deviation is observed.

$$d = d_0 + AC - BC^{3/2} \quad \dots (4)$$

where A and B are constants specific to salt and d and d_0 are densities of salt solution and pure solvent respectively. On transforming equation (4) we get equation (5)

$$\frac{d - d_0}{C} = A - B \sqrt{C} \quad \dots (5)$$

Thus a plot of $\frac{d - d_0}{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} should be linear with A=intercept and B=slope of the plot. The values of the constants A and B of equation (4) estimated from these plots are given in Table 5.

TABLE 5—THE VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS
A AND B OF ROOT'S EQUATION

Composition of Ethanol%	A	B
10	0.119	0.2000
20	0.187	0.5125
30	0.292	1.0267
40	0.415	1.3571
50	0.190	0.2400
60	0.275	0.9000
70	0.240	0.7400
80	0.545	0.2500
90	0.341	-0.4267

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